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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Iqtisodiy fanlar / Economic Sciences/ Экономические науки

1. **Abdullaev, Alisher Makhmudovich** 7
Institutional reforms as a key driver of entrepreneurial activities in Uzbekistan
2. **Ahunova Marifat Khakimovna** 15
Influence of the pandemic on the development of innovations in the world
3. **Iyosov Asrorjon Akhrorjon Ugli** 23
Prospects For Industrial Export Cluster Development

Pedagogika fanlari / Pedagogical sciences/ Педагогические науки

4. **Mikheeva Alexandra Ivanovna** 31
Physical education and physical activity in modern lifestyle

Physical and mathematical sciences / Fizika-matematika fanlari / Физико - математические науки

5. **Axmedova Gavxarxon, Maxmudova Ozodaxon** 40
Non-standard solutions of trigonometric equations
6. **Esanov Nuriddin Kurbanovich, Almuratov, Shavkat Narpulatovich, Jurayev, Uktam Shavkatovich** 51
Free vibration of three-layer shallow spherical shells
7. **Kosimova Makhbubakhon Yakubjanovna** 57
Use interdisciplinary links to improve the quality of students' learning
8. **Nasirov Tulkun Zakirovich, Toxirova Go'zal Sadullayevna** 65
The diffusion as the investigation object in optic materials
9. **Xolmurzayev Abdirasul, Alidjanov Adiljan** 73
The use of methods of projective geometry in the construction of projections of shapes with predetermined conditions

Texnik fanlar / Technical sciences / Технические науки

10. **Akhmedov Jamoldin Djhalolovich, Jurayev Uktam Shavkatovich** 82
Formation of landscape architecture on the territory of samarkand in antiquity and the middle ages
11. **Dusmatov Abdurahim Dusmatovich, Akhmedov Akhadjon Urmonjonovich, Mavlonova Oygul Uljaboyevna** 90
Interlayer shifts of two-layer combined cylindrical shells taking into account temperature loads
12. **Nurmatov Doniyor Olimjon ugli, Juraboyev Asilbek Tolibjon ugli, Toshpulatova Barchinoy Ravshanovna** 98
Tasks and features of transport and its landscape development in modern urban planning theory

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- Advertisement* 107
- Our publications* 113

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INSTITUTIONAL REFORMS AS A KEY DRIVER OF ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN

Abstract: *Modern entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan is considered as a target group of ongoing reforms and, most importantly, as a driving force of transformations in the socio-economic and socio-political spheres. The analysis carried out by the author showed that at the moment entrepreneurial activity is carried out through the institutions of market infrastructure - a set of interrelated design and technological, information and production and organizational systems. Conclusions of the article: the government should think about the post-crisis period of development, develop a deeply thought-out long-term program of targeted projects for the modernization and technical re-equipment of the basic sectors of our economy, the introduction of modern innovative technologies designed to give a powerful impetus to Uzbekistan to achieve new frontiers that ensure the competitiveness of Uzbekistan in the world market.*

Keywords: *institution, institutional environment, institutional conditions, entrepreneurship, transformation, the economy of Uzbekistan.*

ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ РЕФОРМЫ КАК КЛЮЧЕВОЙ ФАКТОР ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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Аннотация: Современное предпринимательство в Узбекистане рассматривается как целевая группа проводимых реформ и, самое главное, как движущая сила преобразований в социально-экономической и общественно-политической сферах. Проведенный автором анализ показал, что на данный момент предпринимательская деятельность осуществляется через институты рыночной инфраструктуры - совокупность взаимосвязанных проектно-технологических, информационных и производственно-организационных систем. Выводы статьи: правительству следует задуматься о посткризисном периоде развития, разработать глубоко продуманную долгосрочную программу целевых проектов по модернизации и техническому перевооружению базовых отраслей нашей экономики, внедрению современных инновационных технологий, призванных придать мощный импульс Узбекистану для достижения новых рубежей, обеспечивающих конкурентоспособность Узбекистана на мировом рынке.

Ключевые слова: институт, институциональная среда, институциональные условия, предпринимательство, трансформация, экономика Узбекистана.

Introduction

Institutional conditions for small business formation should be viewed as a collection of rules and processes that compel small business subjects to adhere to established rules and standards. Even modest institutional structure dynamics have a noticeable, if not decisive, effect on subsystems, particularly entrepreneurial formations. The institute, rules and specific guarantors of rules are all required components of the institutional prerequisites for small business formation.

In contemporary Uzbekistan, dramatic macroeconomic adjustments are underway, with the ultimate goal of implementing the transition to an open, socially-oriented market economy. In this sense, the company structure is undergoing change as a result of resource, conjunctural, and institutional variables.

In Uzbekistan, entrepreneurship is viewed as a target group for ongoing reforms and, more crucially, as a driving factor behind socioeconomic and sociopolitical transformations. At the moment, entrepreneurial activity is facilitated by market infrastructure institutions - a collection of interrelated design, technology, information, manufacturing, and organizational systems [1],[2]. It enables the whole entrepreneurial cycle - from the germ of an idea to its final practical manifestation as a specific product or service [3]. To function effectively, the entrepreneurial institutional system should also have a favorable regulatory environment and an efficient method for introducing enterprise products [4]. As a result, the problem of institutional infrastructure formation is one of the most significant and pressing. Simultaneously, all components of entrepreneurship's institutional infrastructure - interaction with public authorities, financial institutions, availability of technological and production capacity, transparency

and accessibility of information - continue to fall short of meeting tough competitive market conditions and promoting entrepreneurial activity's economic efficiency growth. Additionally, the situation is exacerbated by considerable interregional disparities in entrepreneurial institutional provision.

Economic management market conditions and the need to overcome the global financial and economic crisis, as well as the elimination of the pandemic of coronavirus infection COVID-19, necessitate an intensification of efforts to boost economic dynamics [6]. This is especially true for firms in the real sector of the economy.

In conjunction with the foregoing, entrepreneurship has been highlighted as a priority sector for the country's economic development in Uzbekistan and is promoted by the state [7]. Uzbekistan increased 18 points in the World Bank's annual Doing Business survey during the last three years.

Materials And Methods

The entrepreneurial theory began with the works of representatives of the classical school of political economy, R. Cantillon and J.-B. Say, who coined the term "entrepreneur" and emphasized his capacity to take variable-income risks and perform management and coordination functions overproduction factors. Entrepreneurship theory was further developed in the works of H. Magoldt and J. Thünen, who viewed external environment uncertainty as a source of entrepreneurial income. Entrepreneurs were viewed as innovators and creators by representatives of the German historical school (M. Weber, W. Sombart, G. Schmoller, and others). J. Schumpeter defined entrepreneurship as the capacity to create novel combinations of conventional factors of production.

Further development of entrepreneurship theory is associated with the names of F. Knight, who developed the position of external environment uncertainty as a source of entrepreneurial income; J. Shackle, who analyzed the role of time in economic theory; the neo-Austrian school (L. Mises, F. Hayek), which analyzed entrepreneurship as a process; D. McClelland, and T. Schultz, who studied entrepreneurial motivation, and so on.

Representatives of the institutional orientation, such as T. Veblen, J.K. Galbraith, and J. Commons, made significant contributions to the development of the theory of entrepreneurship. The application of institutional methodology enabled the content of the agent contradiction and the firm's essence as a network of contracts to be revealed (J. Akerlof, A. Berle, R. Coase, J. Means, etc.).

W. Baumol, R. Villigol, and J. Panzar, among others, attempted to integrate the category "entrepreneurship" into the standard economic model. The findings of studies on the factors affecting entrepreneurialism are presented in the works of C. Dean, S. Zar, and A. Thomas, among others. The relationship between economic growth and entrepreneurial development was examined using neoclassical analytical tools, as reflected in the works of Z. Griliches, E. Mansfield, M. Nadiri, M. Porter, P. Romer, and R. Solow, among others.

The fundamental concepts of entrepreneurship and small business in the context of institutional transformations are articulated in the works of internationally renowned economists such as J. Galbraith [8], D. Dixin [9], P. Drucker [10], A. Marshall, A. Smith [11], B. Santo [12], K. Tateisi [13], A. Hosking [14], and J. Schumpeter [15]. Among the most significant studies on various aspects of small business development in the CIS, we should highlight the work of authors such as L. Abalkin[16], V. Avtonomov[17], A. Blinov[18], T. Koichuev[19], O. Krivoruchko[20], M. Lapusta [21], A. Orlov[22], E. Primov [23], V. Rube [24], F. Shakhmalov[25], and A. Yudanov[26].

A. Hikmatov[27], B. Berkinov[28], M. Ikramov [29], N. Makhmudov, M. Tursunkhojaev, Z. Khudayberdiyev, V. Baturina, and D. Trostyansky, among others, conducted studies on the peculiarities of this sector of the economy's formation and development.

A. Akhmedieva, U. Validjanova, O. Ismailova, L. Ishmukhamedova, S. Salaev, I. Tursunov, E. Ergashev, and M. Eshov, among others, devoted their dissertations exclusively to the development of small businesses and private entrepreneurship under new institutional conditions. They focused primarily on regional or branch-level solutions to this problem. However, the focus of research on the problem has shifted somewhat recently from analyzing general issues facing small businesses (their place and role in the economic system, in resolving social problems, and employment issues, for example) to analyzing the factors impeding their development and identifying conditions for small business activation. At the same time, practice demonstrates that despite the state's efforts at various levels, from national to regional, we cannot expect a significant improvement in the situation. This is due to both the multifaceted nature of the small business phenomenon and the diversity of conditions under which it operates. As a result, despite the abundance of publications devoted to various aspects of small business, the study of this issue requires additional development. The institutional conditions governing the entrepreneurial structure in Uzbekistan, in particular, have not been empirically studied.

The study's theoretical and methodological framework was established by the concepts and hypotheses that defined the principles of entrepreneurial activity. The study drew on works that formulated theories of entrepreneurship, innovation and innovative development, and state regulation of the economy, among others. The set of scientific problems was solved through the application of general scientific methods for the study of economic processes.

Results And Discussion

In 2016-2022, a number of systemic measures aimed at creating conditions for doing business and attracting foreign investment for small and private businesses, which are the foundation of Uzbekistan's economic development, were adopted. In October 2016, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan S. Mirziyoyev "On Additional Measures to Ensure Accelerated Development of Entrepreneurship, Comprehensive Protection of Private Property and Qualitative Improvement of the

Business Climate" was issued [30]. The Decree is aimed at creating an even more favorable business environment by abolishing all types of unscheduled and counter-inspections and eliminating barriers. The document pays particular attention to the adoption of effective measures to ensure the dynamic modernization of small and private businesses and stimulate their export activities, which must become the main direction of economic growth in the development of industries and regions, providing employment for the population, and also provides for additional measures to further encourage the participation of small businesses and private entrepreneurship in exports.

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to radically improve the system of state protection of legitimate interests of businesses and further development of entrepreneurship" of June 19, 2017, as well as the Decree "On improving the organization of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan" a deep reform of the Chamber of Commerce and Industry by reviewing its objectives, functions and powers is implemented [31,32].

In order to radically improve the business environment, to create the most favorable conditions for doing business, reduce, simplify and increase the transparency of all types of procedures related to the activities of enterprises, the introduction of generally accepted in world practice, the system of criteria for assessing the business environment and on this basis to further increase the international rating of the business and investment climate in Uzbekistan, the President issued a Decree # 4455 "On measures to further radically improve the business and investment climate in Uzbekistan" on 18 July 2012.

According to the adopted document, the ministries of economy and finance, the Central Bank together with the interested departments and structures in accordance with the methodology adopted by the World Bank and its division of the International Finance Corporation to form the report "Doing Business 2017: Equal Opportunities for All" carried out extensive work on the factor analysis of the business environment and introduction of evaluation criteria and indicators that determine the country rating[33]. The government has a strategic task to increase the country's rating according to the criteria of the "Doing Business" report [34].

In order to further involve the population in entrepreneurial activities and create additional conditions for legal employment, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan #PP-4742 dated 08.06.2020 was adopted. "On measures to simplify state regulation of entrepreneurial activity and self-employment" [35]. According to the document, the country introduced a procedure according to which:

- Registration of self-employed persons is carried out in a notification procedure through a special mobile application or personal account of the taxpayer with the issuance of a matrix bar code (QR-code), certifying the fact of registration as self-employed, with the cancellation of the procedure for issuing temporary labor certificates;

- self-employed persons pay social tax for 2020 in the amount of not less than 50 percent of the amount of the basic calculation amount, regardless of the time actually worked as a self-employed person, the amount of which is fully referred to the off-budget

Pension Fund and on which the amount of earnings for calculating the pension in the manner prescribed for individual entrepreneurs is determined;

- The requirement that self-employed persons have no right to hire workers or have an employer remains;

- state re-registration of legal entities - subjects of entrepreneurship when changing their location (mailing address) is not required in the absence of tax arrears in significant amounts by implementing a notification procedure;

Registration of individual entrepreneurs in the state tax authorities is carried out at the place of entrepreneurial activity during their state registration (re-registration);

- The certificate of state registration of an individual entrepreneur is issued with a picture of the individual entrepreneur on it.

In addition, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction, the Ministry of Justice and the Chamber of Commerce and Industry introduced from 2021 an information system "Business Navigator", which allows the real-time use of services that facilitate entrepreneurial activities.

In this context, the potential of the middle class emerging in Uzbekistan as a result of the development of small and private business, a natural supporter of effective institutions for the protection of property rights, is important. The relevance of the problem, its scientific and practical importance, as well as the insufficient development have determined the writing of the monograph, its object and subject, its logic and structure.

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